

Franziska Baumann

“The Echo I Touch” De- & Embodiment
in spatial Vocal Performance Art

Colloquial Paper

Video of presentation can be found [here](#)

Myths of Disembodied Voices – The Echo I Touch

**1st Person
vocalist**

Disembodied
Vocalist

**2nd Person
Gesture modalities**

Communication

**3rd Person
disembodied voice**

With
Embodiment

- model of aspects of meaning-making
- metaphors for powerful universal concepts of De- & Embodiment in spatial Vocal Performance Art
- Flow of music-making

The Echo I Touch

De- & Embodiment in spatial Vocal Performance Art

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"The disembodied voice speaks to me, sings to me, enchants me, screams for my attention as if it is asking: listen to me, hear me, feel me! Don't be 'afraid of vocal experimentation! Come and sing with me! Touch the riddle of my body! Feel the skin of my resonance! Dance with me in the space! Throw me in the air and catch me again! Together we will be in the momentary of voice, body and space. I welcome that invitation, as much as I can.

Abstract

When using technology such as gesture-controlled live electronics, an expanded field of vocal art performance opens up with the potential to reveal a multitude of vocal extensions and compositional strategies that question the relationship between body, gesture and sound as we know it. The boundaries between the human voice, on the one hand, and the computationally manipulated, bodily and in real-time controlled, but yet disembodied voice, on the other, become increasingly blurred.¹ Through this practice a hybrid in the aesthetic emerges. Motion sequences, which are visible, can add an additional meaning to the sound creation. The gestural communication can serve the understanding, but can also contrast it, put it in a different light or even create a false conclusion (Trugschluss).

Most of performers use interfaces as controllers in the sense that it is supporting the music they want to do. My view is that we need to deepen the question of body presence of the vocalist and to ask about gesture composition and the meaning making of its mapping strategies. The possibility to compose with a mapping machine individual gestures connected to sound processes is a major enabler of creativity.

Tailor made interactions open up a hybrid field in the aesthetic perception. Motion sequences, which are visible, allow for an intuitive approach to the understanding of the energy control which deals with sound creation. Questions occur on the mediation between the presence of being a singer and on the other hand gesturally controlled dis-embodied voices (acousmatic voices).

Approach

From the perspective of a vocalist, composer/performer my main research objective in this hybrid field would be the question of how to integrate body and gestures using all sorts of sensor interfaces and inherent mapping strategies in a more efficient and creative way. Thus in the search for new compositional and performative strategies in spatialized vocal processes of embodied and disembodied voice.

My approach looks for implementation of models to define characters for gesture composition. Instead of starting from the musical gesture and its functional way of controlling I would like to begin to analyze and categorize the body presence and gestures of singers using interfaces in spatialized musical environments. Therefore I am looking for models and a vocabulary which allows composers and singers to expand compositional strategies for performing gestural live electronic vocal performance.

In a further step, this conceptual framework is also intended to provide a basis for gesture compositions in the field of gestural vocal live performance and machine learning based mapping strategies.²

Keywords:

Contemporary Vocal Art Practices, Performing Gestural Live Electronic Music, Interactive Staged Music Performance and Movement, Composing with 3D Ambisonic, Acousmatic and Disembodied Voice, Custom Musical Instrument (DIY), Digital Musical Instrument (DMI), Extended Vocal Techniques, STEIM, Sampling Practices for Vocal and Musical Improvisation, Improvisation and Real-Time Composition, Digital Score, Vocal Personas, Vocal Sound Dance, Imaginary Vocal Body, Aesthetic of Uncertainty and In-Between, SensorGlove as Instrument and Body Extension

¹ Compare Franziska Baumann: *Interfaces in der Live Performance*, in Harenberg/Weissberg: Klang (ohne) Körper, p.75: "Die Grenze zwischen natürlicher und elektronischer Klangerzeugung verschwimmt. Der Körper kann nicht mehr alleiniges 'Interface für die Lesbarkeit der Musik sein" [The boundary between naturally and electronically generated sound becomes blurred. The body cannot be the sole 'interface for interpreting music' anymore.]

² This project is part of a four year research application: *Anticipation of Musical Gesture in the Framework of Generative and Immersive Multimedia Spaces*. With Prof.Dr. Teresa Carrasco, Cathy van Eck, Cédric Spindler and Benoit Piccand, Bern 2021.

Brief history of the SensorGlove

As a singer, composer, improviser my special focus lies on the application of gesture-controlled live electronics, namely the SensorGlove, the first version of which I built in collaboration with Frank Baldé and Jorgen Brinkman 2001 at STEIM, Studio for electro-instrumental music, Amsterdam. Their philosophy of body-close electronic instruments corresponded to my idea of combining electro acoustic composition & live processing with vocal performance on stage without being tied to a mixing console and faders. As I experience gestures as musical extension of the voice, I opted for an interface with sensors, built into a glove.

Figure 1. STEIM's SensorGlove & Belt
Krakau AudioArt Festival 2005

Since with the years the possible amount of processed data could be realized on smaller and smaller chips, it was possible to realize the former SensorLab application on one small Arduino chip. In 2016 the live electronic equipment has been completely new built from the bottom by Berne based Electro engineer Andreas Litmanowitsch and Arduino Programmer Stephan Rothe. If I had to wear additional to STEIM's SensorLab Glove a belt with several boxes, it has become possible to fix sensors and all electronic parts in the SensorGlove itself. This allows me to switch more flexibly between myself as an acoustic singer and a singer with live electronics.

Figure 2. SmartGlove Torun- PL, 2017

Another advantage of the new application is that with the new equipment I independently can compose gestures variabilities coupled to the sound process. With the old SensorLab software C++ every small change of compositional ideas between gesture and sound I had to let reprogram by programmer Daniel Repond. The STEIM's software JunXion endows me with great flexibility and playfulness regarding compositional ideas of gesture and related sound control and creation as I can compose the mapping of gestures and connected sound process myself. Nevertheless, even if it is possible to technically implement every idea we imagine, the respective surfaces of software guide our creative thoughts and form part of the respective "digital score"³.

³ Craig Vear describes "The Digital Score" as a paradigma shift from a place of documentation to a space for creativity.

Sensor Interface in Vocal Performance Art A Hybrid in the Aesthetic Perception

Digital instruments and their respective interfaces are, with regard to gesture and sound, to a certain extent *Black Boxes* as the connection between gesture and sound is random and can be arranged freely. In the case of interface applications which permit gestural control, they force the performer to consciously opt for an artistic decision concerning relationship between gestures, sound production and control. Whether a poker-faced musician with a laptop generates high-energy music or a performer stages an imaginary sound ballet by using sensors: the connection between gesture and sound no longer reveals itself to the audience through the 'surface'.

Over the course of centuries, we have become used to a certain kinds of relationships between sound, the instrument and what we see in a concert. On a violin, the pressure and speed of the bow plays a major role in regulating the volume. The interpreter's images of movement and gestures, which are linked to the instrument have been established. In the process, the body itself has become the interface to the 'interpretability' of the music.

Sensors and their respective expressiveness

Figure 3. Sensors and their respective expressiveness

To a certain extent the specific characteristics of sensors and their respective expressiveness ask for certain gestures. For example with an accelerator it may be difficult to initiate precise controlling over a continuous linear parametrization. As this sensor measures acceleration it is better suited to hit something on or switch off with a gesture whereas for example with an ultra sound sensor one can measure something precisely within a linear distance. This interplay of "necessary movements" and communication of ideas through music and gestures opens up various artistic perspectives on body sculptures in movement and sound.⁴

Figure 4. Model for gestures and mapping

⁴ The term *body sculptures defines choreographic, instrumental, geometrical and meta ideas of gestures

Sensor Interface as an Instrument, Object or Medial Body Extension

Figure 5. SensorGlove as a prop

The SensorGlove interface itself creates an aura that creates certain expectations. The visual appearance creates affordances of inherent purpose, expected function and intention of the object itself like any sensor Interface whether it is a MIO wristband, video or motion tracking, standalone sensor objects etc.

Depending on the characters of gestures and related sound processes during a performance the SensorGlove Interface oscillates between instrument and body extension. As an object with its visual appearance it may refer instrumental character or a medial extension of the body. When I use instrumental gestures such as stroking, plucking, beating, the instrumental character comes to the fore. When the imaginary of voices in space and my physicality meet in gestural communication, the SensorGlove is rather an extension of the body.

The SensorGlove is an interface that I have to practice to articulate preconscious musical intentions, in the field of creative intention, acquired praxis, instinct, intuition and the magic of the moment. Technical processes have to be transferred to body-consciousness and I have to know all possible technical traps and mistakes in order not to fall out of the creative flow of making music during a performance.

Voice as a Special Case

The voice is in musical sense a special case as it provides us our most physical instrument without an external interface, while instruments are always used as a medial extension of the body. The breath in the function of the exciter is mediating between internal and external space of the human body. The interior of the body acts as resonance space, which is projected into the external space.

Disembodied Voice – Dance with the Unchained Voice

The acousmatic and spatialized voice opens up a more radical vocality than that of the acoustic voice alone. The voice decoupled from the body, from the person, could be seen as a new imaginary persona. The performer lends his or her body to the voices released into space. These voices are not only a sound emission of the performer's body, this disembodied voices may produce an imaginary body, a vocal double: bodyless voices in the room invite the listener to conjure up various imaginary bodies. These imaginary bodies can act as invocations brought to life by certain attitudes, gestures, facial expressions, hand, arm, and shoulder movements, as well as by the acoustic gestures that go beyond body images and visible attitudes. It is a virtual experience in which the vocal bodies created, respectively the echo of my own voice can be touched in space. The interactive technology, the interfaces, serve, among other things, to leave voiced fingerprints, or to express several acoustic personalities and manipulate them *vis à versa*.

In this sense I would like to claim that in interactive interface performance a combination of third person perspective (the imaginary vocal sounding body of the disembodied voices) and first person perspective (singer) is fundamental to reveal the position between body and sound.

The second person perspective would then be the relationship between the singer's body and the vocal body that is created in virtual space. This is done by composing gestures which locate body and gesture movement in the environment, so that I understand the vocal sound objects and their movements in space quasi physically as the action of a counterpart. This I - You relationship can provide a framework for the gesture as a communicative act or act of social interaction, entertainment and intentionality.

Myths of Disembodied Voice

In the myths we know disembodied voices such as those of Sybillen, Sphinx, Narcissus and Echo⁵. Imaginary bodies can act as invocations brought to life by certain attitudes, gestures, facial expressions, hand, arm, and shoulder movements, as well as by the acoustic gestures that go beyond body images and visible attitudes. The nature of these vocal sound bodies, however, depends on the reception of the viewer, or listener.

As a singer I quasi lend my body to the voices released into space. The interactive technology - the interfaces - serve, among other things, to leave voiced fingerprints, or to express several acoustic personalities and manipulate them reciprocal. Therefore disembodied vocal bodies remind us that the imaginary, the phantasy, is not only the result of a spiritual disorganized attitude, but always also an embodiment of it.

Figure 6. communication scheme for embodied and disembodied voice

Methods and expected Contributions

Case studies

Based on my earlier research of gesture qualities from instrumental, geometric, choreographic gestures and meta ideas I will hypothesize types of modalities of gesture composition for sensor live electronic interfaces. In case studies with a group of selected internationally known vocal artists using sensor interfaces I wish to analyze and categorize their body presence and gestures. According to the following points I will explore how various conceptions of live interface use might change meaning-making.

- 1) Artistic and Substantive Input of the Vocalist
- 2) The Body Presence of the Vocalist
- 3) Economy of the Interface Practice, Visual Surface and Technical Means
- 4) Gesture Vocabulary, Universally Recognisable Key- Gestures
- 5) Classify gestures of meaning making
- 6) Characteristics of Disembodied Voices & Sounds

Establishing Gesture Based Performance System

Practically I wish to get an overview of utilized commercially available sensor controllers like the HotHand, Wave Ring, MIO Sensor Armband, Apps for I-Phones, tablets etc.

In collaboration with our research group I will design a basic interface with gestural sensor controllers which can be mapped into clear and simple actions, and determining the number of parameters that can be held in mind without visual feedback. This interface system shall contribute with staged/theatrical context and with the need for mobility.

⁵ Weigel Sigrid: *Die Stimme als Medium des Nachlebens*, S.28 in Kolesch, Doris und Krämer, Sybille 2006. *Stimme*. Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp

Practical Evaluation and Project Output with Vocal Ensemble

With this experimental setup I wish to work with a group of vocalists and observe how they interact with various controllers, and experiment with varying levels of gestural control of parameters, also with machine learning coding. With the development of such a modular basic sensor interface I wish to define new ways for gesture composition to bridge the gap between aesthetic and technology and how can they convey meaning in a new imaginary way apart from or as a combination of instrumental, gestural, geometric and meta-idea gestures.

In regard to embodied and disembodied voices I will design three steps of possibilities where the acoustic and the disembodied processed vocal signal as two separate instruments converging in one space. First I will evaluate and develop performative gestures based on heard sound gestures in 3-dimensional space and research how sound may invite gesture. Then I will design mapping strategies for the gesture options and third I will combine both and explore the communicative aspects in between 1st and 3rd person.

My overarching goal for this research project is to expand vocabulary and practical possibilities for gestural sensor live electronic interfaces in spatial vocal performance art.

I wish to design models of aspects of meaning-making for mapping strategies and compositional and performative strategies for powerful universal concepts of de- & embodiment in spatial vocal performance art.

Performances during the research project are documented. One public project a year and two symposiums will take place during the four year period. An exchange and cooperation with selected international partners is intended.

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Research Papers & Links

Trondheim ICLI 2020 All Papers on:

<https://live-interfaces.github.io/liveinterfaces2020/program/>

Baalman, Marije (2020) *Mapping the question of mapping*

Brandtsegg, Øyvind (2020) *An interface to an Interface to an Interface*

Brandtsegg, Øyvind and Tidemann, Axel (2020) *Shape, An adaptive musical interface that optimize the correlation between gesture and sound*

Guérin-Garnett, Nigel, (2020) *Machines in the Creative Process, Limitations Through Choreography*

Moore, Thomas R. Hybrid Conductor (2020) *Case Study and Analysis of Alexander Schubert's Point Ones*

Norderval, Kristin Electrifying Opera (2020) *Amplifying agency for opera singers improvising with interactive audio technology*

Visi, Federico Ghelli and Tanaka, Atsu (2020) *Towards Assisted Interactive Machine Learning: Exploring Gesture-Sound Mappings Using Reinforcement Learning*

Other Papers

Schacher, Jan, and Patrick Neff (2016) "Moving Through the Double Vortex: Exploring Corporeality in and Through Performance Creation." *Journal for Artistic Research*, no. 12 (Winter 2016).

[online cite-bib](#)

Schacher, Jan (2016) "Gestural Performance of Electronic Music—A "NIME" Practice as Research."

Leonardo 49, no. 1 (February 2016): 84–85.

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Links

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Fiebrink, Rebecca, Wekinator open source software: <http://www.wekinator.org/>

ICST Zürich, Institute for Computer Music and Sound Technology: <https://www.zhdk.ch/forschung/icst>

Nowitz, Alex artist website: <https://nowitz.de/>

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SoundDome as an Acousmatic Instrument, John Coulter Auckland: www.sounddome.org

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